

Magnetic Field Analysis of an Electric Motor using Finite Element Method

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Abstract—In the domain of electrical engineering, the design and optimization of electric motors are crucial for achieving higher efficiency and performance. Magnetic field analysis plays a fundamental role in understanding the behavior of electric motors, and the Finite Element Method (FEM) has emerged as a powerful tool for accurately measuring and analyzing the magnetic field behavior of an electric motor. This paper presents an in-depth exploration of the magnetic field analysis of an electric motor using the finite element method. It covers the theoretical parts of FEM, its application to magnetic field analysis, and discusses the significance of this technique in optimizing electric motors for various purposes.

Index Terms—Finite element method, Magnetic Field, Magnetic flux linkage, parameter.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world Electric Motors are one of the most used electrical devices and the demand is growing. Induction motor are the most used type of electrical motors. Therefore, increasing the machine performances and reducing of the leakages are one of the main concerns. The main operation principle of a motor is based on the attraction and repulsion between rotor and stator magnetic fields. Electric motors convert electrical energy into mechanical energy through the interaction of magnetic fields. The performance of an electric motor is directly influenced by the distribution of magnetic flux within its components. The aim of this work is to model and describe magnetic field of the induction machine and find the magnetic flux linkage by finite element method through MATLAB.

II. METHODOLOGY

The finite element method (FEM) is a numerical technique that is used to perform finite element analysis of any given phenomenon. The FEM divides complex geometry of a structure into smaller, manageable elements. Here, we conducted finite element analysis on the magnetic field of an Electric Motor.

Fig.1: Electrical Motor

Finite element methods (FEM) use most of the times a variation principle. According to the variation computation, solving a differential equation in a field and under certain boundary conditions is equivalent with minimizing, in that field, a functional corresponding to the differential equation with its boundary conditions. A functional integral is an integral expression, a function that depends on the unknown functions. The functional integral has a finite value. [1] The problem concerning solving the system of differential equations of the electromagnetic field with some boundary conditions is equivalent with the problem of finding a function which gives the integral minimum by which the energy system is expressed.

Let's consider the energy functional associated with the arbitrary three-dimensional field D:

$$\zeta = \int_D \left(\left(\int_0^{\vec{E}} \vec{D} d\vec{D} \right) - \left(\int_0^{\vec{B}} \vec{H} d\vec{B} \right) + \left(\vec{J}\vec{A} - pV \right) \right) dD$$

where $\vec{D}$, $\vec{E}$, $\vec{B}$, $\vec{H}$ are the vectors associated with electric and magnetic fields, $\vec{A}$ is the magnetic vector potential, V is the scalar electric potential, $\vec{J}$ is the density vector of conduction

electric current and is the volume density of electric charge (Silvester Ferrari, 1996). The first parenthesis of the integrand represents the difference between the volume density of the electric and magnetic energy. The second parenthesis represents the difference between the volume density of interaction energies between the conduction current and magnetic field, as well as between the electric charge and the electric field. The interaction energies are equal to the work done by the field forces in order to bring the current density, respectively electric charge, from infinity, where the potentials are considered ($\vec{A} = 0, V = 0$), to the states characterized by the values $\vec{A}$ and V

The electromagnetic potentials $\vec{A}$ and V define the vectors $\vec{E}$ and $\vec{B}$ of the electromagnetic field:

$$\vec{E} = -gradV \quad (1)$$

and

$$\vec{B} = rot\vec{A} \quad (2)$$

The energy functional associated with the stationary magnetic field produced by the direct currents and in case by permanent magnets is expressed as:

$$\zeta(\vec{A}) = \int_D \left(\int_0^{\vec{B}} \vec{H} d\vec{B} - \vec{J}\vec{A} \right) dD \quad (3)$$

Two-dimensional problems of stationary magnetic field are by definition problems in which the unknown, the vector magnetic potential, is orientated as one axis of the coordinate system and depends on the other two coordinates of the system (Stammborg, 1995).

2D problems in Cartesian coordinates (x,y,z) are called parallel-plane. The current density $\vec{J}$, is oriented by the axis Oz and the magnetic vector potential has the structure $\vec{A} = A\vec{k}$ and its orientation is also by the axis Oz. The magnetic induction is written as:

$$\vec{B} = rot\vec{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{i} & \vec{j} & \vec{k} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ 0 & 0 & A(x,y) \end{bmatrix} = \vec{i} \frac{\partial A}{\partial y} - \vec{j} \frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \quad (4)$$

The square of magnetic induction is:

$$\vec{B}^2 = (rot\vec{A})^2 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial A}{\partial y} \\ -\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

The magnetic vector potential $\vec{A}$ is obtained by minimizing the functional:

$$\sigma\zeta(\vec{A}) = 0 \quad (6)$$

In the case of stationary magnetic field, the functional is related to the physical size of a known issue, such as the total energy of the magnetic field inside the domain D:

$$W_m = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \vec{H} \vec{B} dv \quad (7)$$

The magnetic energy is located in the magnetic field with the volume density W_m :

$$W_m = \frac{\vec{H} \cdot \vec{B}}{2} = \frac{(\vec{B})^2}{2\mu} \quad (8)$$

Eckhardt describes in detail the solution to this problem. The magnetic field density is reduced to the following scalar equation (Stammborg, 1995; Eckhardt, 1978):

$$W_m = \frac{1}{2\mu} B^2 - J \cdot A \quad (9)$$

In the case of the parallel-plane fields, the boundary conditions are:

$$A(x, y) = f(p), p \in C_D \quad (10)$$

$$-\frac{1}{\mu} \frac{dA}{dn} = g(P), p \in C_N \quad (11)$$

where Eq. (10) represents the Dirichlet boundary conditions on the boundary C_D and Eq. (11) represents the Neumann boundary conditions on the boundary C_N .

The domain of computation for a two-dimensional problem (Andrei et al. 2012)

$$l = \int_S \left(\frac{1}{2\mu} \left[\left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] - J \cdot A \right) dx dy \quad (12)$$

where the function represents the magnetic energy computed on the surface S_Γ bounded by the curve Γ .

The unknown function $A(x,y)$ for node i is determined by minimizing the functional:

$$\frac{\partial l}{\partial A_i} = \int_S \left[\frac{1}{\mu} \left[\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial A_i} \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial A}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial A_i} \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial y} \right) \right] - J \frac{\partial A}{\partial A_i} \right] dx dy = 0 \quad (13)$$

Therefore, the following equations system is obtained:

$$f_k = \sum_{z=1}^{q(i)} \frac{\partial l}{\partial A_i} = 0 \quad (14)$$

A_i is the magnetic vector potential of the node i of the element z .

The differentials involved in Eq. (13) are written according to the shape functions and have the following expressions (Stammborg, 1995; Eckhardt, 1978):

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} = \sum_{k=1}^{n(e)} A_k \frac{\partial \alpha_k}{\partial x} = \sum_{k=1}^{n(e)} A_k \cdot b_k \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial y} = \sum_{k=1}^{n(e)} A_k \frac{\partial \alpha_k}{\partial y} = \sum_{k=1}^{n(e)} A_k \cdot b_k \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial A_i} \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{\partial \alpha_i}{\partial x} = b_i \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial A_i} \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial y} \right) = \frac{\partial \alpha_i}{\partial y} = c_i \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial A_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial A_i} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n(e)} \alpha_k A_k \right) = \alpha_i = a_i + b_i \cdot x + c_i \cdot y \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\partial l_e}{\partial A_i} = \int_S \left[\frac{1}{\mu} \left[\left(\sum_{k=1}^{n(e)} b_k \cdot A_k \right) \cdot b_i + \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n(e)} c_k \cdot A_k \right) \cdot c_i \right] - J \alpha_i \right] dx dy \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial l_e}{\partial A_i} = 0 \quad (21)$$

A homogeneous medium is considered, thus the magnetic permittivity μ is constant for each finite element, being independent of the x and y coordinates:

$$\frac{\partial l_e}{\partial A_i} = \frac{D}{2\mu} [A_1 (b_1 b_i + c_1 c_i) + A_2 (b_2 b_i + c_2 c_i) + A_3 (b_3 b_i + c_3 c_i)] - J \frac{D}{6} = 0 \quad (22)$$

where D is the determinant computed. Eq.(22) can be written under matrix form as:

$$\frac{\partial l_e}{\partial A_i} = \frac{D}{2\mu} \begin{bmatrix} (b_1 b_i + c_1 c_i) & (b_2 b_i + c_2 c_i) & (b_3 b_i + c_3 c_i) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \\ A_3 \end{bmatrix} - j \frac{D}{6} = 0 \quad (23)$$

The functional is sum of contributions other than the ne" finite elements. Stationarization of the functional requires (Stammberg, 1995; Silvester Ferrari, 1996):

$$\sum_{e=1}^{ne} \frac{\partial l_e}{\partial A_i} = 0 \quad (24)$$

where „ne" is the total number of finite elements.

$$\{F\} = [K] \cdot \{A\} - [P] + [Q] \quad (25)$$

The term [P] is used for the case of the source" type elements where the current density $\vec{J}$ is non-null, and the term [Q] is used for the case of the elements which have in

one of the sizes a non-homogeneous Neumann boundary. By assembling there" equations in Eq. (24), a linear system of equations of magnetic vector potential values in the mesh nodes is obtained (Ioan, 1993).

III. FINITE ELEMENT METHOD IMPLEMENTATION

FEM is used in many fields of science and engineering to obtain approximate solutions for the partial differential equations to be solved. Its basic concept is that although the behavior of a function may be complex when viewed over a large region, a simple approximation may be sufficed for a small subregion. In practice, it utilizes a variational problem that involves an integral of the differential equation over the problem domain by dividing it into a large number of non-overlapping subregions, each with a simple geometry. Over each subregion the solution of the partial differential equation is approximated by a polynomial function. These polynomials have to be pieced together so that where the edges of adjoining elements overlap the field representations must agree to maintain continuity of the field. Then the variational integral is evaluated as a sum of contributions from each element resulting in an algebraic system with a finite size than the original infinite-dimensional partial differential equation. When enough small regions are used, the approximate solution closely matches the exact one. The advantage of breaking the domain down into a number of small elements is the problem transformation from a small but too complex into a big but relatively easy to solve [2]. One-quarter part of the machine cross-section geometry is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2:Discretization of the induction machine geometry.

Linear triangular elements are used for discretizing cross-sectional area of the induction machine such that the mesh

coordinates during computing process can be accessed rapidly . In this approach, the FEM meshes of the cross section of the machine are divided into two parts, which are the stator and the rotor, each including a part of the air gap. Meshes of the two parts are generated separately. The air gap is divided into two layers, one of which is to the rotor, and the other is to the stator. This means that the stator and the rotor meshes are generated once at the beginning and then can be used without any further change throughout the computing . Electromagnetic problem analysis starts with Maxwell's equations [2]:

$$\nabla \cdot E - \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} = 0 \quad (26)$$

where E is the electric field intensity, ρ is the charge density, ϵ is the electrical permittivity.

$$\nabla \cdot B = 0 \quad (27)$$

where B is the magnetic flux density.

$$\nabla \times E + \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$\nabla \times B - \mu \left(J + \epsilon \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} \right) = 0 \quad (29)$$

where μ is the magnetic permeability Ohm's law can be written with J and E quantities [2]:

$$J = \sigma E \quad (30)$$

where J is the current density, σ is the medium conductivity. For the time-invariant cases (28) and (29) are simplified into:

$$\nabla \times E = 0 \quad (31)$$

$$\nabla \times B - \mu J = 0 \quad (32)$$

In a magnetostatic problem FEMM goes about finding a field that satisfies (27) and (32) via the magnetic vector potential approach. Flux density is written in terms of the vector potential A [31] is represented as follows:

$$B = \nabla \times A \quad (33)$$

$$\nabla \times \left(\frac{1}{\mu B} \nabla \times A \right) = J \quad (34)$$

If linear isotropic magnetic material is used, (34) simplifies to:

$$\nabla^2 A + \mu J = 0 \quad (35)$$

Electric scalar potential V is used for solving electrostatic problems:

$$E = -\nabla V \quad (36)$$

$$\nabla^2 V + \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} = 0 \quad (37)$$

Low frequency time harmonic magnetic problems are also solved when the field is oscillating in one fixed frequency. In

this case the equation is:

$$\nabla \times \left(\frac{1}{\mu_{eff} B} \times \alpha \right) + \sigma \nabla V - \vec{J} \omega \sigma \alpha = 0 \quad (38)$$

where, ω is the oscillation frequency, $\vec{J}$ is the phasor transformation of the applied current sources, μ_{eff} is the effective magnetic permeability, α is the complex amplitude of the phasor transformation [2].

IV. MATLAB CODE

```

clc
clear all
close all
set(0, 'defaulttextinterpreter', 'Latex');

%Define motor parameters
mu0=4*pi*10^-7;% Vacuum permeability
N=100;% Number of nodes
L=.1;% Length of the motor (meters)
coilCurrent=5;%Current in the coil(
    Amperes)

%Discretization
dx=L/(N-1);
x=linspace(0, L, N);

%Initialize matrices
K=zeros(N, N);
F=zeros(N, 1);

%Loop over each node
for i=2:N-1
    %Stiffness matrix coefficient
    Ke=-mu0/dx;

    %Assemble element stiffness matrix into
    global matrix
    K(i, i-1:i+1)=K(i, i-1:i+1)+[1 -2 1]*Ke;

    %Contribution to the source vector
    Fe=coilCurrent*dx;

    % Assemble element source vector into
    global vector
    F(i)=F(i)+Fe;
end

%Applying boundary conditions
K(1, :)=0;
K(1, 1)=1;
F(1)=0;
K(N, :)=0;
K(N, N)=1;
F(N)=0;

```

```

%Solve the system of equations
A=K\F;

%Calculate magnetic flux linkage
fluxLinkage=sum(A)*dx;
fprintf('Total Magnetic Flux Linkage: %.4
f Weber\n', fluxLinkage);

%Calculate magnetic field B
B=mu0*A;

%Plot the magnetic field
plot(x,B);
xlabel('Position (m)');
ylabel('Magnetic Field (T)');
title('Magnetic Field Analysis of an
Electric Motor');

```

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Calculated Total Magnetic Flux Linkage is 331.5390 Weber

fig.3 :Magnetic field versus Rotor position

The magnetic field represents the strength of the magnetic flux at each rotor position. The graph[fig.3] exhibits a pattern based on the motor's design and characteristics. We see that the graph doesn't show a linear or consistent pattern due to factors such as magnetic saturation, non-uniform air gaps, or asymmetrical winding arrangements. As a result, we get valuable information about the motor's performance, identifying any irregularities or abnormalities in the magnetic field distribution.

Fig.4 : The BH curve of stator material1001[3]

The B-H curve [fig.4] is generally used to describe the non-linear behavior of magnetization that a ferromagnetic material obtains in response to an applied magnetic field.

The B-H curve is usually used to describe the magnetization properties of such materials by characterizing the permeability, which is defined as:

$$\mu = \frac{B}{H} \quad (39)$$

where B and H represent the magnetic flux density in tesla (T) and the magnetic field intensity in ampère per meter (A/m), respectively. [4]

VI. CONCLUSION

The finite element [FEM] method has showed it's effectiveness and importance in the analysis of the magnetic field in electric motors. Through this method, we can accurately predict and visualize the distribution of the magnetic field for understanding and enhancing the motor's performance. The analysis provides us with important insights into the behavior of the magnetic field. By identifying potential issues like magnetic saturation, uneven flux distribution, we can make design modifications to solve these problems and improve overall performance.

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